

ANALYSIS OF MECHANICAL STRENGTH DATA FROM

HYBRID FABRIC LAMINATES OF GLASS AND GRAPHITE FIBERS

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Abstract

An experimental study of the mechanical properties of graphite/glass/graphite interply hybrid composite laminates subjected to pure tension and pure flexure is reported. The investigation includes single-graphite, single-glass and hybrid composite laminates. Straight side test coupons with dimensions of 200 mm x 14 mm and various numbers of layers were fabricated by hand lay-up molding method. Epoxy resin served as the base matrix material. The types of layup of fabric warp directions include: 0° , 45° , 90° , $[0_3^0/45_2^0/0_3^0]$ and $[0_3^0/45_2^0/45_3^0]$.

Emphasis is given to the studying of the strength-deformation behavior and the associated crack patterns of hybrid composite laminates, for monotonically-increasing longitudinal elongation and angular deflection. Stress-strain characteristics and crack patterns distinctive to each type of the specimen tested are presented. Mechanical strength data for hybrid composite laminates indicate the improvement in material characteristics over the single-graphite fabric laminates.

Introduction

The hybrid composite laminates have been widely used in many engineering applications for its superiorities in structural performance. Experimental and theoretical studies to determine the mechanical properties and fracture behaviors of carbon/glass, graphite/Kevlar-49 and carbon/Kevlar-49 hybrid constructions are reported in Ref.1-5. Theoretical methods were developed and verified by comparing predictions with experimental results of these constructions.

In the present investigation, a graphite/epoxy fabric laminate which was designed for ablative parts in aerospace engineering was reinforced by a close woven E-glass fabric cloth for improving its mechanical properties and fracture behaviors. Information here is of interest not only (a) graphite-glass hybrid composite laminates but also (b) single-graphite and single-glass composite laminates. Both tension and flexure tests were conducted on an Instron testing machine. The crack patterns produced during each of these strength-deformation excursions for each type of specimen were observed.

Experiment

The experimental studies were based on the following three objectives: (a) to determine the stress-strain behaviors of single-fiber and hybrid composite laminates under pure tension and pure flexure, (b) to determine the maximum load-carrying ability of these constructions, and (c) to examine the crack patterns of various types of layup laminates subjected to pure tension and pure flexure.

All of the test specimens were fabricated by hand lay-up molding method through the same process as those reported earlier in Ref.6. The Carborundum GSGC-2 graphite plain woven fabric cloth, Burlington Style 1582 E-glass satin woven fabric cloth and the Ciba-Geigy Araldit epoxy resin are the constituents of the laminated composite plates. The configuration of fabrics is shown in Table I. The straight side test coupons with dimensions of 200 mm x 14 mm are cut from these laminated plates in various angles with respect to the fabric warp direction as shown in the schematic in Fig.1. The specimens characteristics are also in the following Table II.

The portion of the study concerned with the behavior of single-fiber composite laminates consisted of three series of tests: (a) warp direction test, (b) fill direction test, and (c) 45-degree direction test. In the other portion of this experi-

Table I Configurations of Fabrics

Fabrics	Graphite* (GSGC-2)	Glass** (1582)
Thickness (in)	0.0175	0.0140
Weave Pattern	Plain	8-Shaft Satin
Warp (threads/in)	27	60
Filling (threads/in)	23	56
Breaking Strength		
Warp (lbs/in)	50	525
Filling (lbs/in)	40	500
Type Yarn Used		
Warp	75-1/2	150-1/3
Filling	75-1/2	150-1/3

* Carborundum Company.

** Burlington Glass Fabrics Co..

Fig.1 Tensile Test Specimen

Table II Specimen Characteristics*

Test Program	1	2	3
Laminates Construction	Graphite/Epoxy	Glass/Epoxy	Hybrid/Epoxy
Specific Gravity	1.33	1.82	1.41
Lamination	5 plies	10 plies	6-ply graphite 1-ply glass
Total Thickness (mm)	2.14	4.02	2.87

* CIBA Epoxy resin Araldit 507 was used. Fiber weight content 60%.

ment, three other series of tests were conducted for developing the mechanical behaviors of the hybrid composite laminates. These series were performed on the following types of laminations: (a) $[Gr-0_3^0/Gl-0^0/Gr-0_3^0]$, (b) $[Gr-0_3^0/Gl-45^0/Gr-0_3^0]$, (c) $[Gr-0_3^0/Gl-45^0/Gr-45_3^0]$.

The test arrangement employed to apply an unidirectional tension force to the test specimen is shown schematically in Fig.2, also, the strain-measuring arrangement is shown. The loading was applied by a calibrated Instron Universal Testing Machine in constant crosshead speed of 1 mm/min for test program 1 (graphite/epoxy) and 3 (hybrid/epoxy), (see Table II), and of 2 mm/min for test program 2 (glass/epoxy). Two Micro-Measure-

Fig.2 Strain Measurement

ments EA-06-250BF-350-L strain gages were mounted perpendicular to each other on the central portion of each tensile specimen. Both the longitudinal and transversal strains were measured and plotted on an X-Y Recorder. On the reverse of the gage-mounted surface, an Instron strain gage extensometer G-51-11M (gage length 25 mm) was clipped and connected with the X-Y Recorder installed on the testing machine. Thus, the load vs. axial elongation curves were plotted.

In flexure test, a three-point loading frame was set up on the Instron machine. The crosshead was displaced with the same loading rate as those applied in tension test. According to ASTM D790-71, all the test specimens were deflected until a 0.05 mm/mm maximum strain was reached. An X-Y Recorder recorded these load-deflection information.

The experimental results obtained in this study are presented in graphical, tabular and photographic form in the next section.

Results and Discussion

A total of ninety-six specimens was tested in this experimental study. The deformation either in tension or in flexure was measured as a function of the applied loads. The curves of stress-strain are calculated and plotted for every single test. Summarily, their typical characteristic curves of each test series are presented. Also, during the test, failure modes of specimens were observed and photographed. It is clearly that the "maximum load-carrying ability" is determined by the load-carrying ability at the initial crack as discussed in the follow-

ing paragraph.

Single-Fiber Composite

The test results for single-fiber composite laminates are summarized in Table 3. It is seen that the strengthes and moduli of glass/epoxy laminates are higher than those of graphite/epoxy laminates. Apparently, it results from the use of a glass fabrics with high-strength yarn and close woven pattern, which has been studied earlier in Ref.7.

Fig.3 illustrates failure modes for tensile specimens. The failure modes of the 45-degree fabric laminates were observed to have large deformation in both the longitudinal and transversal directions, which cause high values of Poisson's ratio as depicted in Table 3. The top view and side view of crack patterns for flexural test specimens are indicated in

Table 3 Mechanical Properties of Specimens

Composites	Strength (10 ³ psi)		Modulus (10 ⁶ psi)		Poisson's Ratio	
	Warp Direction	Fill 45-deg Direction	Warp Direction	Fill 45-deg Direction	Warp Direction	Fill 45-deg Direction
Graphite/Epoxy	15.044	-	1.423	-	0.182	0.333
Glass/Epoxy	59.111	52.829	3.086	2.997	0.125	0.500
TENSILE TEST						
FLEXURAL TEST						
Graphite/Epoxy*	21.393	-	1.217	-	-	-
Glass/Epoxy **	43.303	39.486	2.840	2.481	-	-

* Support span 2.0 in.

** Support span 4.0 in.

Fig.5 and Fig.6. It is noted that a crack failure normal to the fiber direction was always followed with an interlayer delaminating failure.

The curves of Fig. 4 and Fig.7 show the stress-strain characteristics for single-fiber composite laminates under the loading of tension and flexure respectively. As shown, the pre-failure curve is essentially linear and gradually turns to level off prior to failure or initial crack. As indicated in Fig.7, with further increases in strain after initial crack, one encounters a succession of new cracks accompanying each of which is an abrupt drop in the load-carrying ability of the test specimen.

Hybrid Composite

The stress-strain characteristics for hybrid laminates are

(a) $[0], [45], [0_3/45_2]$
Graphite/Epoxy

(b) $[0], [90], [45]$
Glass/Epoxy

Fig.3 Tension Test

Fig.4 Stress-Strain Curve of Specimens Tested under Uniaxial Tension Load.

Fig.5 Flexure Test of Graphite/Epoxy Specimens

shown in Fig.10. It is noted that in all cases the load-carrying ability was dropped significantly at initial crack.

The tensile failure modes for each hybrid construction were distinctive, as illustrated in Fig.8. For example, the $[0_3^0/0^0/0_3^0]$ laminate exhibited a larger ultimate strain than that of the $[0_3^0/45^0/0_3^0]$ laminate, because the 0-degree glass fabric lamina provided higher strength and stiffness. However, both of these two constructions had smaller ultimate strains than that of the single-graphite laminates. Also, it should be noted that the glass fabric layer was not broken but elongated.

As shown in Fig.9, the flexural failure modes are indicated. It is apparently that the crack failure normal to the fiber direction was intercepted by the 0-degree glass fabric lamina in the $[0_3^0/0^0/0_3^0]$ laminates and arrested by the 45-degree glass fabric lamina in the $[0_3^0/45^0/0_3^0]$ laminates. Thus, in post-failure

Fig. 6 Flexure Test of Glass/Epoxy Specimens
[45], [90], [0]

Fig.7 Stress-Strain Curve of Specimens Tested under 3-point Flexure Load.

Fig.8 Tension Test of Hybrid/Epoxy Specimens.

Fig.9 Flexure Test of Hybrid/Epoxy Specimens

range most portion of loading was carried by the glass fabrics, as shown in Fig.10 the constant portion of the curve.

A summary of the tensile and flexural properties (ultimate stress, σ_u ; initial elastic modulus, E ; initial proportional limit stress, σ_y) of hybrid composite laminates is given in Table 4. In order to compare the mechanical properties of single-graphite and hybrid composite laminates, some nondimensional ratios are calculated and included in Table 4, such as σ_y/σ_y^{Gr} , σ_u/σ_u^{Gr} , E/E^{Gr} , where the superscript Gr represents Graphite. A slight improvement in structural performance is obviously indicated.

A laminate construction of $[0_3^0/45^0/45_3^0]$ were also tested. See Table 4, Fig.10, Fig.8 and Fig.9 for it's experimental data and failur modes.

Conclusion

The present effort has been devoted to an experimental study of the mechanical behaviors and failure modes of single-graphite, single-glass and graphite/glass hybrid composite laminates subjected to pure tension and pure flexure. Data show that the " hybridization " is efficient in improving the composites properties and changing the crack behaviors. Extension of the present studies to include (a) a laminate construction with higher glass/graphite ratio, e.g., $[\text{graphite}_2/\text{glass}_3/\text{graphite}_2]$ (b) a predamaged hybrid laminate with a circular hole would be valuable in developing an information base for both empirical and theoretical purpose.

Fig.10 Stress-Strain Curve of Hybrid/Epoxy Specimens under Tension and Flexure.

Hy-1: $[0_3/0/0_3]$, Hy-2: $[0_3/45/45_3]$

Hy-3: $[0_3/45/0_3]$.

Table 4 Mechanical Properties of Hybrid Laminates^a

Specimen Tested	$[0_3/0/0_3]$		$[0_3/45/0_3]$		$[0_3/45/45_3]$	
	Tension	Flexure	Tension	Flexure	Tension	Flexure
σ_y (10^3 psi)	7.555	15.387	4.089	15.575	5.333	15.104*
σ_u (10^3 psi)	15.706	22.302	13.218	22.185	12.231	20.768
E (10^6 psi)	1.693	1.289	1.714	1.286	1.474	1.258
σ_y / σ_y^{Gr}	1.334	1.007	0.722	1.019	-	-
σ_u / σ_u^{Gr}	1.044	1.043	0.879	1.037	-	-
E / E^{Gr}	1.190	1.059	1.205	1.057	-	-

^a Laminate Construction: $[\text{Graphite}_3 / \text{Glass} / \text{Graphite}_3]$.

* 0-degree tension side; 7.551 for 45-degree tension side.

Note: (Tension) $\sigma_y^{Gr} = 5.662 \times 10^3$ psi.

(Flexure) $\sigma_y^{Gr} = 15.281 \times 10^3$ psi.

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